

EXPRESSION OF PLACE RELATION AND TOPONYMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information about prepositions in English and their alternatives in Uzbek and also Toponymy, the branch of onomastics concerned with the study of toponyms or place names, has been considered by most scholars to be a discipline of convergence (or of "synthesis"), i.e., a discipline concerned with a multiplicity and variety of knowledge and which can, therefore, be approached from many different perspectives. In practice, toponymy can be said to involve a considerable number of fields of understanding - fields that do not stand in juxtaposition to one another but which are rather very closely interrelated. From this perspective, we believe that it genuinely responds to the profile of knowledge that Edgar Morin, in one of his recent works (Morin, 2001), identifies as interdisciplinary: i.e., one which overlaps with other fields without becoming blurred, which forms relations on the basis of reciprocity and which rules out the possibility of a simple hierarchical relationship. By virtue of its interdisciplinary nature, the relationship that is established between toponymy and the rich diversity of subjects that converge in its study is not so much one of competition but rather one of instrumental cooperation.

Nowadays, English is an international language. It can also be called a universal language. English has the second largest number of speakers. It is an official language in 70 countries. English is a simple and easy language to learn. Because it uses the Latin alphabet. In addition, in English, the Latin alphabet is presented in its most "pure" form - 26 main letters without superscripts. In addition, English is considered an analytical language. In analytical language, grammatical meanings are expressed using auxiliary words, word order and intonation. Prepositions are very important in expressing these relationships in English. A preposition is an auxiliary word that shows the relationship of a noun or pronoun to other words in a sentence. Prepositions indicate the relationship between clauses and sentences. In the Uzbek language, these relationships are implemented with the help of agreements,

auxiliary word groups and other additions. In this case, words and forms are formed by adding suffixes without changing the root and base of the word. These are agglutinative language features. This is why the Uzbek and English languages differ from each other. There are about 50 prepositions in the English language, which are of great importance: aboard, about, above, across, against, along, among, around, behind, below, beside, between, beyond, by, down, during, except, for, from, in, inside, into, like, near, of, off, on, out, over, past, regarding, since, than, till, towards, under, until, up, upon, versus, with, without etc. These prepositions are divided into three types according to their lexical meaning: 1. Prepositions of time. 2. Place prepositions. 3. Prepositions of direction. First, let's look at prepositions of time. At, on, in are used for time. These prepositions are translated into Uzbek in the form of the suffix "- da". The preposition at is used for specific time and hour. For example,

At 12:30 - soat 12:30 da

At night - tunda

The preposition on is used for days of the week and month. For example,

On March 14 - 14-martda

On Sunday - yakshanbakuni

The preposition in is used for long periods: months, seasons, years and centuries. For example, In July - iyuloyida In summer - yozfaslida

In 2000 - 2000-yilda If we use the above prepositions now as locative prepositions, they refer to the location of a thing or a person. At - translates as "next to". It is translated into Uzbek as "-da".

For example, At the blackboard - doskayonida At the window - derazayonida At home - uyda, At the cinema - kinoteatrda, In - is more likely to be translated as "within". It refers to the location of a person inside something. For example, In the hotel - mehmonxonada, In the water - suvda, In the box - qutiichida, In the room - xonada The preposition on corresponded to the word "over" in Uzbek. This preposition indicates the location of an object or a person in relation to a surface. On the way - yo'lda, On the wall - devorda, On the roof - tomida, On the table - stolustida.

Now let's look at some prepositions of direction. To, towards, from, away (from), through, in (into), inward(s), outward(s), out of are used to express the sense of direction. Toward(s) is translated as auxiliaries such as "sari", "qarab". It represents a direction that is relatively close. However, the direction is not over. For example, The boys are going toward the field - yigitlardalatomonketishdi. To - to, towards. This preposition indicates the end point of the route. For example, She is going to the University - u universitetgabormoqchi.

The name of a particular region of the earth was important to determine the language and many toponymic studies for this purpose by geographers carried out. A. Humboldt, H. Vamberi, J. Tonnele, N. Nadejdin, Scientists such as A. Vostokov, A. Kastren, P. Semyonov-Tyan-Shansky, L. Berg made a significant contribution to the development of scientific toponymy. For example, academics "Exercises for amateurs of etymology" written by A. Vostokov in 1812 prefixes and suffixes of geographical names in the article divided into several groups based on similarity, and this is a coincidence concluded that it is not. If we look at the etymology of Uzbek toponyms that some of the works are devoted to the study of microtoponyms of districts or cities. Because the narrower the scope of the toponymic object,

the more valid the scientific conclusions. From this point of view, the scientific researches of such scientists as T.Rakhmatov, J.Latipov, H.Kholmuminov, O.Aripov, A.Aslanov, S.Burievare noteworthy. A.Turobov seriously studied the linguistic analysis of ethnonyms and ethnonames on the example of materials of Samarkand region. O.Begimov defended his dissertation on the linguistic study of the assimilation layer in toponyms. H. Burieva studied the problems of historical toponymy of Tashkent in the late XIX - early XX centuries. An enthusiastic scientist T.Enazarovalsoplayedasignificant role in the expansion of toponymic research in Uzbekistan. The candidate's dissertation was devoted to the analysis of place names in the Shahrisabz region, while his doctoral dissertation covered the lexical basis of toponymsand the problems of etymological research. The emergence of toponymsAtoponym is alsoageographical name. But toponymsare proper nouns. Proper nouns are derived from common nouns (appellate) in the relatively laterstages of language development. It is said that there were no proper nouns in ancient languages. Indigenous peoples of Australia, Africaand the Americas - the language of the aborigines - have very few proper nouns. In such languages, common nouns andphrasesactas pronouns. Such phrasesare becoming more and more stable. People refer to the familiar smallareaaround them with phrases such as "Fishing Lake", "Flooding Valley", "Sheep Pasture", and "Pig River"(SuyunQoraev, Toponymy, Tashkent 2006).

Such phrasesandrelated names, which describe specific geographical objects, graduallybecame famousbecause of the lack of proper nouns. The emergence of geographical names is a result of the concretizationandindividualization of the general concept. This is how cognate common nouns become toponyms. For example, the word 'apple' is ageneral term for appleorchards, so it remains arelative term. When this concept is individualized, when it begins to represent a specific object, and thus expresses a particular concept, it becomes a proper noun. The word that becomes atoponym often takes the form of atypical toponym with the discovery of a new meaning, resulting in suffixes specific to toponyms. Uzbek toponyms, especiallyoykonims, are characterized by affixes such as 'istan' (Shuristan, Bogistan), iya (Uzbekistan, Mingiya), -kor (Pakhtakor, Lalmikor), -cha (Kudukcha, Buloqcha) (SuyunQoraev, Toponymy, Tashkent 2006 p-26). In some toponyms the meaning of the words before becoming atoponym is clearly known, in other toponyms it is partially preserved, in others it seems unknown under the same names, and in others it is completely lost. Therefore, it is not correct to maketoponymsthat are not clear by changing them a little, as such names can be valuable linguistic and historical relics of ancient languages. Most toponyms have undergone many grammatical andsemanticchanges before they came to their present form. Depending on their origin, toponyms can be of two types: naturally occurring toponymscreated by people andartificiallycreated toponyms.

Original geographical namesare a product of folk art. Most toponyms do not appear suddenly. Early geographical objects, such as villages, may be called differently. For example, depending on the relief, the name of the people who contributed to the development of the water source, it can be called "someone's-andsovillage", "someone's village". Gradually one of these names wins. For example, it takes the name of the village of the Naiman tribe. In this case, the process of becoming a real toponym is not over, so the toponym is a whole sentence and roughto use, andaccording to the law of savinglexical means of the language, this toponym

finally takes the form of Naiman. Geographical name can also completely change the appearance of a common noun over a long period of time. For example, Zoroastrians are called "Mughals" by Muslims. In Uzbekistan, toponyms such as 'Mughan, Mugkhona' are left to these firefighters. Names like 'Miq, Miqtepa' are a vivid reflection of the word 'mug'. Or khanaqah Khanqa, Dizak (diz, "fortress" in Sogdian) Jizzakh, aqba (Arabic pass) in the form of a hunt, and so on. Some toponymists believe that geographical names, unlike other parts of the lexicon, do not have significant meaning and only serve to distinguish geographical object from others. Phonetic changes can be detected through linguistic research. But it's not true that geographical names don't make sense. This idea denies the role of toponyms as valuable spiritual monuments. Geologists have proved how many valuable underground treasures were found by toponyms. Thus, geographical names represent specific geographical concepts. Over time, the process of generalizing geographical names and representing larger objects takes place. The name of a large area today originally meant a small area, but gradually became the name of an entire area.

The toponymy of the United States is characterized by many nicknames for the names of states, cities, and their inhabitants. According to S. Ulman, there is a law of synonymous shooting, according to which there are more synonyms in the designation of objects of public interest. This means that a popular object will have many names, because as a result of frequent use, one or more of its names will begin to develop other, additional meanings, and on the one hand, if incorrect, on the other hand it is less expressive. The place names of the UK are extremely rich and diverse, mainly due to changes in language and culture. British toponyms contain elements rooted in the languages of at least five different peoples - Celts, Romans, Anglo-Saxons, Scandinavians, French. All of these peoples contributed to the toponymy of the country and brought the English toponyms to their present state.

In conclusion, in English, prepositions are functional words that allow you to connect the components of a sentence and make its meaning more clear and precise. It should also be said that in English, prepositions of the same form are used in different meanings.

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